

Home-Based Learning as a Modality: Perspectives and Practices

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Abstract

Parents have an important role in the current learning situation because they need to get involved in the home-based learning of their own children. Children have no choice but to stay home and continue learning. The partnership between teachers and parents has been considered for the smooth implementation of this modality. This paper aims to describe and analyze the life experiences of parent-teachers who are involved in home-based learning. This is phenomenological qualitative research. There were six participants in this study who were selected using the snowball recruitment technique. Essay questions and focus-group discussions served as methods of data collection. In analyzing the textual data, the researcher used content analysis, where he examined, classified, categorized, and synthesized data to form a synthesis. It was discovered that participants were experiencing problems with connectivity, materials, collaboration, time, and socialization as they carried out home-based learning for their children. They believed that key ingredients to success in home-based learning include communication, collaboration, technology, connectivity, and training. After assessing the needs and concerns of the participants, this paper proposed a learning model which is named “Communication, Collaboration, and Reflection or C3 for Home-based learning,” which will address the concerns, needs, and problems being faced by parents, teachers, and children while they are involved in home-based learning as a form of modality not just during the pandemic but even in the new setting. Lastly, PhD students who are centered on qualitative studies served as validators of the proposed learning model.

Keywords: Home-based Learning, Practices, Perspectives, Phenomenology, Learning Model

1. Introduction

The world has been affected by the pandemic since the year 2020. Many aspects have changed, including the landscape of education. Schools have started to adopt trends and innovations in terms of instruction and modality. The commonly heard and used terms are modular learning, blended learning, synchronous and asynchronous learning, and home learning.

Parents have an important role in today’s situation because they need to get involved in the home-based learning of their own children. Children have no choice but to stay home and read learning modules. This is a tedious process because they have to understand the concepts and answer the mandatory assessments. The partnership between teachers and parents has been considered for the smooth implementation of this modality. Based on observations, this process has involved issues and challenges faced by parents, teachers, and children. In the Philippine school setting, where many people have no choice but to switch to home-based learning, noticeable impediments and problems are seen.

Despite the impact of the pandemic on people’s lives, parents have decided to continue schooling their children through home-based learning through printed modules. It is not easy for children, parents, and teachers to partake in this method because it is something new for them. There is really a big adjustment on their part to do the tasks and functions.

2. Review of Literature

Agaton and Cueto (2021) sought to examine the lived experiences of parents on distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines. In their study, educational institutions were closed down and dramatically shifted to distance learning when it comes to instruction. It was depicted in the study that students from marginalized families had poor connectivity and limited access to the technology necessary for online learning. Their study served as a basis for providing inclusive and equitable policy formulation as it considered the perspectives of both parents and learners during and after the pandemic.

On March 16, 2020, schools in the Philippines were closed following the imposition of health protocols and lockdown, which was called Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ). The Department of Education (DepEd) designed a framework termed as Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), which provides guidelines and procedures on how instruction shall deliver education during the time of crisis while ensuring the safety and health of people. The Department of Education sets guidelines on the management and supervision of modalities, assessments, activities, and webinars.

Similarly, Abel (2020) examined the life experiences of Filipino learners during the pandemic as they were immersed in remote learning. His study discovered that challenges include poor and limited internet access, financial difficulties, lack of technological devices, and lack of emotional-social support from parents and guardians.

On the other hand, Limon and Castillo (2016) developed an instructional module on home and family living following the principles and procedures of the ADDIE Model. Bartolome, Mamat and Masnan (2017) have underlined the important role of parent’s involvement in the schooling and education of children. Their literature review has found that it is imperative that schools have to consider the cultural and social diversity of parents when it comes to school involvement. Moreover, in this research, the researchers clearly distinguish and define differences between engagement and involvement of parents in school activities and tasks.

Same situations were seen by Baticulon et al. (2020) in their study in which they found out that barriers to online learning include difficulties in lifestyle adjustment and coping with responsibilities at home and poor communication between teachers and students. Several

universities around the globe have been offering distance education courses and programs to meet the learning needs and diversities of students. They ensure that their program offerings are supported by technology so that learning and instruction will be accessible to all.

Wai-Cook (2020) explained how home-based learning can promote self-directed learning. However, teachers and parents have to nurture and shape children with essential skills to be self-reliant and independent thinkers. Distance education is the most feasible and common pedagogical approach adopted by schools and teachers during the health crisis phenomenon. Learning and teaching have been conducted in home settings which is known as home-based learning. Research proves that the key benefits of home-based learning include independent learning and review of materials at one's own pace. Furthermore, the findings of Wai-Cook (2020) indicated that around the globe, teachers were provided with materials regarding curriculum, pedagogues, digital learning, and technology. The resources however, did not teach or train teachers on how they should collaborate with parents.

Incidents of home-based learning, according to studies, were increasing in 2006. A lot of programs were intended for children from birth to age 5. There are a number of education types and care programs available for children age 5 and younger. Some offer care for the children of busy families as well as educational programs. The said programs are either housed in homes or centers. Pre-schools commonly provide an educational program that centers on the holistic development of children, school preparation, or learning a particular culture or skill. Working families choose to have their children home-schooled for practical reasons (Feeney et al., 2010).

On the other hand, Wen, Gwendoline, and Lau (2021) discussed how knowledge of ICT can prepare and assist schools and teachers in offering home-based courses. They described how important is the role of technology integration in distance education. They also underscored pedagogical and learning factors and aspects of the success of the program.

Meanwhile, Bartolome, Mamat and Masnan (2017) emphasized the crucial role of parent involvement in the home-based learning of their children. In their literature review, they discovered that it is pivotal for schools to identify the social and cultural diversities of parents when it comes to the academic involvement of their children. Furthermore, in their study, they depicted how and why parents have striking differences when it comes to their engagement and involvement in various school activities and programs.

Liberto and Maree (2016) explored practices performed by teachers in home-based learning. Tangible elements considered are syllabus, timetable, and books. In their study, it was also realized that eclectic home educators attempted various educational resources to guide students and parents. Other parents feared that home-based learning would suffer in terms of quality of learning and instruction.

On the one hand, Bubb and Jones (2020) identified and explained key areas encountered by children in home-based learning engagement. They illustrated glaring issues such as creativity, online learning, class participation, development, group tasks, and parent-teacher relationship. Their study also described and discussed the struggles of teachers in designing, selecting, and developing their instructional materials.

Ray (2017) reviewed home-school learner outcomes while focusing on the conceptual theme related to home-based learning and schooling in general. His paper synthesized ideas and concepts on academic achievement, social and emotional aspects, and the success of adults. In many countries such as England, Japan, Mexico, South Africa, Scotland, and Russia, solid evidence showed that home-based learning made noticeable gains in huge numbers and percentages. The rebirth of home-based learning startled many educators, sociologists, historians, and theologians and has captured thousands of families (Rothermel, 2015).

However, limitations were seen in the methodologies used to explore home-based learning (Lubienski, Puckett & Brewer, 2013). Studies in the past have failed to cover and evaluate the limitations and data needed for comprehensive investigations. Other studies employed various psychological measures and constructs to prove that home-based learning was developing better than those who went through traditional classroom setup (White et al., 2007). Medlin (2013) proved in his study that children are acquiring skills, behavior, values, and motivations they need to function as members of a community. He also discovered that home-schooled children had higher GPAs and academic aptitude scores.

Gloeckner and Jones (2013) concluded in their article that home-based learning graduates in higher education institutions performed better in their first year in college compared to traditional high school graduates. The study by Richardson (2011) found minimal correlations between teacher preparation and teacher certification to students' academic performance in public schools. Ray (2013) suggested in his study that the government has to support and promote private home-based learning since, in many students, it was proved to be effective.

In the research review conducted by scholars of Peabody Journal of Education, socialization was defined as the process by which the child acquires skills. Behavior patterns and values for dynamic functioning in the community where he is growing up (Maccoby, 2007). In home-based learning, the roles of parents play an important part, as investigated by Harris (2009). The impact of home-based learning is observed through socialization and the way parents supervise their children, as observed in the study of Grusec and Davidov (2010). Teachers should be engaged with a critical inquiry which is a rigorous, collaborative, and informed activity. In the book of Oliva (2005), constructivist learning holds that the teacher is a facilitator of learning and that students are taught to become responsible for their own learning. Learning is an active process and is acquired through doing or involvement. Basic skills are learned by individuals through authentic situations.

In the progressive school, the scientific method was introduced. It consists of five steps which are (1) identifying a problem; (2) forming a hypothesis; (3) gathering data; (4) analyzing data; and (5) drawing conclusions. In the progressive classroom, cooperation is fostered in the classroom. Most of the cited materials talked about the approaches and issues encountered by teachers and parents in the implementation of home-based learning, as well as their personal involvement in the process itself. The current study, on the other hand, described and analyzed the experiences of parent-teachers being frontrunners in the conduct of home-based learning as a form of modality among public schools. Their views, reflections, and experiences matter in the success of this undertaking. We need to tailor the courses and curriculum to the needs and diversities of the learners to prepare them for cross-cultural and multilingual settings. We can offer a wide array of programs that address their capacities and individualities.

2.1 Objective

This research aims to analyze and describe the life experiences of parent-teachers who have been involved in the implementation of home-based learning as a form of modality. It sought to explore the perspectives and practices of the participants through their conscious experiences. Specifically, it sought answers to the following research problems.

1. What are the challenges faced by participants in the implementation of home-based learning as a modality?
2. How can home-based learning be successfully implemented?

2.2. Research Design

This project paper followed a qualitative method in order to describe and analyze people and contexts. The researcher studied the perspectives of the participants related to events, beliefs, and practices (Gay & Airasian, 2003). Furthermore, phenomenology was the

approach employed by the researcher to study the experiences of people on activities and events during the implementation of home-based learning.

The researcher decided to select participants using *snowball recruitment*, also called *chain sampling*. This is a method suitable for identifying study participants with specific traits, rare experiences, or hidden population cohorts who may be difficult to identify with other recruitment methods. In this method, the researcher asked key informants who knew others who were connected to the traits or qualities sought by the study. The researcher considered possible participants whose cases are information-rich. There were only six participants who qualified to get involved in the investigation based on the principle of saturation. Only striking and obvious traits which met the criteria were picked out carefully and rationally (Marshall & Rossman, 2006).

The participants are LET passers or with a professional education certificate and have units in a masteral program or are currently taking graduate courses. Other selection criteria are the length of teaching experience, participants' conscious awareness, involvement in home-based learning modality, and parent-teacher status. The researcher intended to have more than 10; however, due to the inclusion criteria and exposure to the phenomenon, only six participants qualified for the investigation process. Originally, 12 participants were tapped; however, due to time and availability, the number was reduced to 6, considering all factors and the convenience of the final participant-teachers.

The researcher collected data using essays and online focus group discussions. He scheduled his sessions with his participants by finding out the most convenient time they could offer. After getting the approvals, he immediately arranged appointments and schedules with them. The distribution of essays with open-ended questions took place in the month of December 2021, while follow-up regarding the codes and categories occurred in the month of January 2022. In this data-gathering phase, the researcher sought the assistance of google meet and electronic mail so that sending and receiving information and data would be secured and convenient.

3. Findings, Analysis, and Discussions

The researcher analyzed and categorized the responses of the participants in the virtual interview and focus group discussion. Participants expressed concerns about time, communication, connection, and instructional materials as threats or problems in home-based learning. On the other hand, they believe that training on technology and modality, communication and collaboration between parents and teachers, and proper assessment should be looked into by school authorities and stakeholders for a successful home-based learning implementation.

Most of the participants expressed in their responses and reactions that assessment, connectivity, and communication are the major problems they have been facing since the pandemic came into the country. This is supported by the actual interview and online discussion by the researcher with the participants in which key points were clarified and raised in connection to the essay responses of the said participants. Nanquil (2021) further asserted that despite the global pandemic disruption and crisis, quality education should continue by adopting the trends and issues.

The participants shared their views regarding the successful implementation of home-based learning. Their views and insights were taken from their experiences being collaborators and tutors during the conduct of the modality itself. Evidently, not all experiences and observations were positive because there were perceived challenges, as well. Regarding the responses of the participants, the researcher patiently examined, described, and categorized the ideas and discourses to form a synthesis.

Other participants also underscored the value of motivation and independent study for the success of home-based learning. The views of participants called for training for both parent-teachers, collaboration and communication, preparation of instructional materials, support from the government, and connectivity. Furthermore, instructional materials like modules must be thoughtfully polished.

All these areas and key points require thoughtful reflection from both teachers and school authorities and/or officials. There should be discussion and collaboration on how they can address the aforementioned issues that require immediate action.

Through a questionnaire with essay questions, the researcher collected responses which were converted into textual data. Descriptions and categorization played an important role in forming and making conclusions.

Participants believed that problems in home-based learning start from connectivity, communication, and connection among parents, children, and coaches or teachers. If they do not have stable connectivity, most likely, they cannot communicate with experts; websites and consultations are impossible. Moreover, participants stressed their thoughts on the place of collaboration and technology as methods and instruments to effectively conduct the home-based learning modality for their children. If parents, they said, have more time to spend with their children and if they have knowledge or orientation on how the modality is conducted, somehow the tension and confusion will be reduced and addressed. The reflective paper written by Nanquil (2021) discussed how challenging it was to cope with the challenges and changes brought about by the health crisis in the new setting.

He described the importance of communication and collaboration in sustaining and protecting the social and emotional aspects of learners. He stated that in developing the macro-skills of the learners, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing as well as their critical thinking skills, communication and collaboration play an essential role.

The views of participants call for training for both parent-teachers, collaboration and communication, preparation of instructional materials, support from the government, and connectivity. Furthermore, instructional materials like modules must be thoughtfully polished. All these areas and key points require thoughtful reflection from both teachers and school authorities and/or officials. There should be discussion and collaboration on how they can address the aforementioned issues that require immediate action.

3.1 Synthesis

What needs and challenges were experienced by the participants in their implementation of home-based learning?

Based on the data, participants expressed concerns on important areas that hamper and affect the implementation of home-based learning, such as time, internet connectivity, assessment, collaboration and communication between parents, children, and teachers, training, instructional materials, and well-being of learners. If parents and teachers were trained, oriented, and upskilled in pedagogies and approaches, there could be improvements. Another major concern is connectivity since many families have insufficient funds to sustain internet connectivity.

How can home-based learning be successfully implemented?

Home-based learning can be implemented successfully if parents and children have stable and reliable connectivity at home, appropriate training and orientation, well-thought instructional materials, and time for interaction at home and online. Teachers need to communicate and collaborate with parents in monitoring, assessing, and guiding their children. This partnership is proven to be one of the effective ways to address problems in home-based learning.

4. Implications of the Study

The global health crisis paralyzed many aspects and structures. Unlike before, people from different parts of the world were unmindful and carefree about the events and happenings surrounding them. The times are really changing, so to speak. In two years, when this health crisis hit the whole world, transactions, events, classes, and movements of people were severely affected and devastated. It is factual that many schools ceased operations, classes shifted from onsite to distance and flexible learning, businesses lost gains and profits, a decrease in the number of enrollees, and food shortage. Students are facing big adjustments to the modality being implemented by the school. Before the pandemic occurred, students could then freely and conveniently move and wander to different places. Going out then did not require a facemask and face shield because there was no contagious virus as strong as COVID, which could instantly and rapidly contaminate and harm people. Children then have a clear and dynamic mindset since they have nothing to fear. But in this contemporary period, everything was changed by the health crisis. Students fear many things now. They are careful and mindful of their health as they go out. Even when they are in online classes, their well-being and psychological aspects are not in good shape. They feel frightened and anxious because of the gruesome news they view on social media platforms and other websites. The effects of the pandemic are wide, colossal, and tremendous. Evidently, it will take time before normal operations and transactions will go back from their original forms.

In the globalized and digitized educational setting, the Generation Z and Alpha Generation who are adept in technology should be provided with interactive, supportive, equitable, and inclusive instruction. The emerging generation will definitely have characteristics and traits that are somewhat different from the previous generations; that is why teachers need to be flexible and reflective when it comes to designing, developing, implementing, and evaluating instructional goals and learning experiences.

Even teachers are immensely affected. They are the frontrunners in the educational setting, so they have to design, prepare, and distribute course modules and other instructional materials assigned by the Department of Education. Teachers have to move in double time. With all the heavy loads they are carrying, many teachers and academicians experience health problems, stress, and anxiety. It is a burden that teachers have to prepare documents and modules, collect the modules from houses or homes, and automatically check papers for recording, reporting to the principal or school head, and computation of grades. While other professionals get the opportunity to work from home, teachers stay home but with numerous tasks and mountains of paper to evaluate. It is never the same scenario.

We can somehow say that the world has been tremendously changed by an enemy which is invisible. Society, in the larger view, is also affected. There were scenes in 2020 when cities, parks, and food chains became lonesome, empty, and serene. There were no customers and people who could stay there and spend time eating and bonding with friends. This event led to the bankruptcy of many establishments. At this moment, people from different places are trying to adjust to the situation. Due to changes in policies and agreements, people and society are trying to gradually regain strength and restore their shape. At the level and aspect of students, teachers, and school, issues and problems on modality were raised, such as the effectiveness and practicality of embarking on online and distance learning. Many schools have started to do shifting on systems and modalities. From traditional settings and practice, schools are now engaged in distance learning and flexible instruction. Teachers and pupils have gone through rigorous training and supervision in order to achieve mastery and exposure to learning management tools, online platforms, curriculum mapping, curriculum design, development and evaluation, and professional-personal development courses.

Parents and teachers should also take time to discuss their observations with the child. In this way, new thoughts and ideas can guide and inform the teacher in preparing and selecting topics and lessons suitable to the needs and diversities of children.

4.1 Proposed Learning Model in Home-Based Learning

Figure 1. C2R in Home-Based Learning

In the automated education landscape, schools and higher education institutions have to try flexible learning modalities to address the changing needs and diversities of children. The responses of participants in the questionnaire and focus-group discussion evidently show that problems in home-based learning are lack of time, poor technology knowledge, limited internet connectivity, pedagogy, and socialization of children. Due to limited connectivity, learners, teachers, and parents find it challenging to connect and collaborate for instructional coaching and planning. Children are experiencing anxiety and similar problems in the social-emotional aspect due to limited socialization since lockdown has been implemented for more than a year due to the ongoing global health crisis. Hence, the researcher decided to design a model which would address the existing problems. This is named C2R, which stands for Communication, Collaboration, and Reflection.

The first-word communication covers all important tools and aspects that contribute to successful communication among parents, children, and teachers. It is true that some parents do not have the time to attend to the needs of their children. They need to spend periods of conversation and socialization with their children to discuss modules and issues regarding their schooling. Internet connectivity and technology such as gadgets and equipment are also included in this area. Through proper training and support from the national and local government units, parents and teachers can have rigorous and relevant professional training on pedagogy, technology, and practices useful

to home education and home-schooling. The communication aspect also allows parents and teachers to stay connected during an age of disruption, such as the phenomenon we have been facing for two years now. The age of disruption and globalism dictates that people need a wired community and society in which connectivity and technology play important roles.

The second component is collaboration. The experiences and observations of participants underscored that children are experiencing anxiety due to limited interaction with family and peers. Parents are creeping in the darkness when they are tasked to instruct and guide their children on how to answer the assessment tasks in the module. As such, they need collaboration with teachers, which is an effective way to address problems, concerns, and issues regarding their children's progress and performance. In this area, conversation, consultation, and coaching are underlined and emphasized to guide and assist children. Collaboration also means that even after the assessment phase, the partnership between teachers and parents does not stop.

The last component is reflection. This serves as an assessment and evaluation of the steps and procedures taken by teachers and parents in implementing home-based learning as a modality of learning. It addresses questions and issues that both parents and teachers encounter throughout the learning journeys of the child. It also invites and involves parents and teachers to schedule a time in which they will discuss everything about the modality and the child. In this aspect, the strategies, approaches, practices, and insights are tackled, recorded, and collected for future endeavors such as educational and action research that will contribute to existing theories and knowledge and will address social issues and academic needs and problems.

5. Conclusions

Most of the participants expressed in their responses and reactions that assessment, connectivity, and communication are the major problems they have been facing since the pandemic came into the country. This is supported by the actual interview and online discussion by the researcher with the participants in which key points were clarified and raised in connection to the essay responses of the said participants.

Parents, teachers, and children are having difficulties in communicating with one another due to connectivity, lack of time, and insufficient knowledge of tools and gadgets. Children are unable to participate and respond actively due to connectivity issues and a lack of support from parents. There is also perceived concern about learning assessment and instructional materials.

Home-based learning will be successful if there is communication, collaboration, and reflection in the implementation of the modality. Parents need training on how they can collaborate and partner with teachers. On the other hand, teachers need retooling, upskilling, and reskilling on instructional materials development and instructional pedagogies in the new normal.

5.1 Recommendations

Problems observed and covered in the investigation may be addressed by the stakeholders for the smooth articulation, implementation, and evaluation of the modality and/or program. There may be a specific training program that can address the social and emotional concerns of children and their guardians and/or parents. Regarding time management, counseling and orientation can be effective ways to tackle such aspects. For the assessment, teachers can assign alternative tasks and authentic assessments such as performance activities, reflective essays, and graphic organizers that learners may answer but with the guidance of parents. It is also necessary that stakeholders, including parents and their children, will be trained and oriented on the values and aspects of integrity in the assessment. The curricula for grades 1-3 may be revised based on the existing needs, problems, and diversities among learners and the transitions occurring around the globe. Activities and assessments must be appropriate, equitable, inclusive, and supportive. Through varied and adaptive instruments, the assessment of learning will be valid, reliable, and relevant to the learners and their performance.

The wired community and global learners are interconnected by the internet and technology. Hence, stakeholders, with the support of experts, have to identify trends and issues that can have an impact on the lives of people who are involved in the use of technology and innovation. Proper training and dissemination should take place and cover all the essential features and skills needed by people. In a changing world affected by the disruption, teachers have to design authentic learning assessments that are learner-centered. This can help them assert and sustain academic credibility and integrity.

While home-based learning is only during the time of the pandemic, favorable results were seen by stakeholders who might indicate that it will become a required modality in the future or it may be blended with another approach or modality that is suited to the individualities and peculiarities of the learners. Parents and teachers may undergo capacity-building training with regard to technology, modality, assessment, and pedagogy. Teachers and parents should work in collaboration so that children can be supervised carefully and efficiently.

The collaboration, communication, and reflection are among the most important elements and constructs that home-based learning needs for successful implementation. In the age of disruption, a wired community is a must, and flexible learning is considered. A training program that aims to leverage teachers and parents may be designed and developed that can address the concerns of both parents and teachers.

Local government units may coordinate and collaborate with pre-school and early childhood teachers for the systematic and successful implementation of modular learning and home-based learning. They can identify the priorities, needs, and funds needed to cover and shoulder that can sustain the program.

Future studies about home-based learning can be conducted by scholars so that new ideas, concepts, and directions can be achieved that will meet the growing and changing needs and problems in the early childhood education programs and advocacies. Other approaches and methods can be employed by future researchers to examine the life experiences and practices of parents and teachers who are involved in home-based learning modalities. Teachers may design instructional materials based on the needs, traits, and learning styles of children. Instructional materials with course outlines must be validated by a pool of experts before distribution and usage.

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Bio-note:

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